

PROJECT-BASED EDUCATION IN SIMULATION AND MANAGEMENT OF PRODUCTION

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Abstract

The contribution presents an approach to implementing project-based education supported by simulation software into the educational process of two related subjects involved in engineering study in the field of applied informatics provided by the Slovak University of Technology. We bring observations and experiences using this method in teaching the management of production systems, which develops the knowledge and skills obtained in the previous course on modelling and simulation of systems. Both subjects aimed to utilise the simulation approach in the modelling and optimising systems for production systems management. The framework we work within employs a lot of interdisciplinary relationships and knowledge relating to programming, system design, operational research, production logistics, and production management.

Considering this, project-based education is a natural choice in this area as an alternative to traditional educational methods. The task within the project is focused on designing and creating a production system model to meet all capacity requirements and optimising output parameters from the point of view of production indicators. After being familiar with the theoretical principles and methods at the beginning of the term, students can apply them in practice when solving a project task with the individual assistance of the teacher, if necessary.

Keywords

Project-based education, simulation, optimisation, production management

1 Introduction

Innovative alternative methods and digital technologies adopted for the educational process make learning more enjoyable for students and, in specific directions, can be more effective than traditional ones. Game-based learning (Backlund & Hendrix, 2013; Wiggins, 2016; Sun et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023), virtual reality-based learning (Kavanagh et al., 2017; Kaplan-Rakowski & Gruber, 2021) or project-based learning (Mettas & Constantinou, 2008; Mioduser & Betzer, 2008; Pérez & Rubio, 2020) belongs to the most popular. They attract the attention of researchers to investigate the most effective way and how to use it in education.

All of the above methods support intensive computational thinking (CT) education. The simulation approach in modelling demands entirely developed CT skills, such as abstract thinking, logic, coding, and logical reasoning (Angeli & Giannakos, 2020).

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1.1 Game-based learning

In improving CT via education, game-based learning (GBL) can play a significant role (Hooshyar et al., 2021). Lu et al. (Lu et al., 2023), Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2023), and Sun et al. (Sun et al., 2021) introduced the results of the meta-analysis and systematic review related to the impact of educational games and game-based learning on students' computational thinking. A similar topic for higher education is studied in the work of Wiggins (Wiggins, 2016).

Udeozor et al. (2023) state that "digital games can immerse learners in simulated real-world environments that foster contextualised and active learning experiences." However, they mention the challenges of applying computer games to assessment. Their work presents a game-based assessment framework for designing assessments for immersive learning environments.

1.2 Virtual reality-based learning

From a perspective point of view, employing virtual reality-based learning in education (VRL) also disposes of substantial opportunity for the enhancement of students' motivation, transfer of knowledge, and development of skills, e.g. in the course of the design of the manufacturing system (Ma et al., 2018), or in special medical training (Pulijala, 2018). In addition, the VRL course content management system powered by artificial intelligence (AI) seems promising for effective personalised, competency-based, and differentiated learning (Zou, 2021). Online learning platforms use AI to measure students' skill sets, capabilities, and interests before recommending the most contextual course content (Roll & Wylie, 2016).

1.3 Project-based learning

Comparing innovative learning methods to traditional ones, according to Helm and Katz (Helm & Katz, 2001), students learn best in informal and interactive situations. This is the substantial attribute of project-based learning (PBL), which can be defined as a student-oriented approach in pedagogy. It encompasses a dynamic classroom work that is assumed to offer students more profound knowledge and skills via active solving of real-world problems.

The main advantage of this alternative method is that it can be a source of joy from discovering knowledge and achieving understanding, which is internally understood as success. Both feelings create a high intrinsic motivation, which is crucial for learning. Also, individual work or work within small teams develops creativity and soft skills (Yasseri et al., 2018).

The application of PBL is widespread, mainly in subjects where the complex overlap of many different areas can be identified. Children can use this method in its simplest form already at elementary school, and a more advanced approach grounded on deeper interdisciplinary relationships and solving complex problems appears in subsequent high school and university studies.

Experiences published in the literature indicate that courses focused on education in fields related to nature, life sciences, and technical subjects have a great potential to invoke more profound interest and curiosity when applying project-based learning. Notable results were observed in acquiring knowledge and skills when applying PBL for education in physics (Holubova, 2008), bioinformatics laboratory courses (Achappa et al., 2020), and design and software engineering (Pérez & Rubio, 2020) concerning university courses. PBL was also successfully applied in teaching molecular biology (Elsamanoudy et al., 2021) or in introductory biology (Burks, 2022).

2 Project-based learning in the education of technical subjects of engineering degree related to simulation and management of manufacturing systems

Manufacturing system design and management of production are related complex engineering areas with the need for cooperated and collected multiple-disciplinary theoretical and practical assistance. Sometimes, it can be challenging for learners to fully understand topics in this field, such as context and relationships. Concerning the experience presented in the literature, PBL implementation provides many opportunities to improve acquiring knowledge with relationships and better insight into the studied subject.

Abella'n-Nebot (Abella'n-Nebot, 2020) proposed a PBL approach with actual manufacturing activities in a four-year mechanical engineering course to improve the learning process. The project focused on planning the manufacturing process of a natural part and performing all the activities required directly on the shop floor to solve authentic real practice problems.

In Serdar's work (Serdar, 2015), the experience and teaching results of PBL implementation in the Manufacturing Processes Course were presented. He mentioned that many manufacturing courses provided students with technical information, but it had to be transformed into appropriate knowledge for actual practice. The goal of design projects was to define a product design through the identification of potential combinations of materials and processes that could generate the desired shapes with the required properties, all this by redesigning an originated existing part.

Pérez and Rubio (Pérez & Rubio, 2020) presented a project-based learning (PBL) experience in a software engineering program at a Spanish university. The work was organised in small, heterogeneous teams. The challenge for students was to solve a software project similar to a real one. Students work on different tasks throughout the project via the strategy of role rotation and documentation transfer.

This contribution demonstrates the implementation of project-based learning into the educational process within two compulsory subjects of a technical focus, which are part of studies of engineering degrees in the 1st and 2nd year for selected fields of study. The subjects Modeling and Simulation of Systems (MSS) and Management of Production Systems (MPS) follow each other smoothly, and all seminars are fully supported by the computer using simulation software Witness Horizon and Excel spreadsheet.

3 Design and implementation of project-based learning and its results

3.1 Modeling and Simulation of Systems (MSS) course

In the MSS course, the first nine weeks of the term were devoted to understanding the essence of critical concepts and their relationships in the field of modelling and simulation of various types of systems and, at the same time, to acquiring skills in work with the software Witness in which we created simulation models. We mixed traditional lectures to explain the new and unknown and seminars based on interactivity with two-way feedback, which controls the learning tempo according to the student's capabilities.

After mastering the creation of simulation models, students learned to analyse the modelled system, experimented with its parameters, and assessed its behaviour and outputs in simulation experiments. In the last four weeks of the term, project-based learning was applied. Each student worked independently on a given complex problem task at his tempo. When solving this, the teacher assisted and appreciated creativity, critical and analytical thinking, and an innovative approach.

3.2 Management of production systems (MPS) course

The MPS course builds on the knowledge and skills acquired in the MSS. Although it is comprehended in a certain sense, more specifically at first sight, because it concentrates on the optimisation of production systems within the framework of systems management, it comprises other interdisciplinary relationships and knowledge from the fields of system design, production logistics, operational research, and production management. With this in mind, project-based learning is directly offered for education.

The student's task is to design and create a model of a flexible production system according to capacity requirements and to optimise its output parameters. At the beginning of the term, after students become familiar with the theoretical principles and methods of designing such systems, they can apply them practically when solving a project task. They learn to experiment, analyse relationships between variables, interpret data, draw conclusions, and share knowledge. They also apply all knowledge and programming skills originated from previous MSS courses.

3.3 The role of the teacher

The teacher works individually with everyone and guides him/her according to the project's actual status. The teacher also prepares materials for individual self-study and explains the basic principles and ideas applicable to all students regardless of the specification of individual tasks, if necessary.

The quality of project results depends on the student's creativity, internal motivation, patience, and ability to observe, analyse, and evaluate. Communication skills and precise formulation of thoughts are also important for successfully achieving the project goals.

3.4 Feedback – students

For students' feedback, we created a short questionnaire about learning experiences and self-study materials. The student's reflection (21 respondents) was primarily positive; they considered both subjects interesting and liked learning them independently. They appreciated the possibility of proceeding at an individual tempo and the teacher's and their mates' support. They also valued the freedom to manifest their creativity in solving project problems. The feedback related to selected responses is depicted in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, resp.

Fig. 1: Student's feedback on a way of acquiring information in both courses

Source: Authors

Fig.2: Reflexion based on student's feedback on a needed assistance

Source: Authors

3.5 Feedback – teacher:

The most appreciated feature of project-based learning from the teacher's point of view was to observe the students' creativity and the opportunity to learn something new from them when the unique solution or procedure was introduced. The teacher also ensured a more pleasant and informal environment and built better relations between him/her and their students.

On the other hand, much information had to be often repeated because the progress in the project was at a different level, and a specific need for assistance in solving the same partial problem appeared repeatedly.

4 Conclusion

Experience with implementing project-based learning in subjects focused on simulation and management of production shows the effectiveness of combining lectures and the project approach. Based on students' predominantly positive feedback, we find it essential that if work is appropriately supported by teacher assistance, this student-oriented approach generates an increase in satisfaction and more profound interest and develops the ability to think independently and work creatively, individually, and in small teams. In the future direction, we would like to employ virtual reality elements in designing a project task.

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